

RAPID DAMAGE ASSESSMENT FROM HIGH RESOLUTION IMAGERY

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ABSTRACT

Disaster impact modeling and analysis uses huge volumes of image data that are produced immediately following a natural or an anthropogenic disaster event. Rapid damage assessment is the key to time critical decision support in disaster management to better utilize available response resources and accelerate recovery and relief efforts. But exploiting huge volumes of high resolution image data for identifying damaged areas with robust consistency in near real time is a challenging task. In this paper, we present an automated image analysis technique to identify areas of structural damage from high resolution optical satellite data using features based on image content.

Index Terms— feature extraction, damage assessment, image texture analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

Remote sensing technologies are being increasingly used for valuable post disaster damage assessment [1]. A variety of sensors both active and passive are available to acquire data. But optical sensors are used extensively due to ease of image interpretation and distribution of data. Huge volume of remotely sensed image data is being produced at sub-meter spatial resolutions and with temporal coverage before and after a disaster event. The goal is to identify and extract damaged areas from the images and to refine the information available to decision makers and first responders during preparedness, rescue and recovery stages of disaster management. Effective disaster management requires reliable and robust estimate of damaged areas caused by the events and is time critical. One of the major hurdles in generating effective decision support information from image data is the lack of effective framework that allows for efficient acquisition, handling and analysis of this voluminous image data in a limited amount of time. Previous works have explored damage assessment from remote sensing images for tsunamis [2], earthquake events

[3] and coastal disaster events [4]. Typically, the pre and post-event images are compared manually to produce damage polygons or thematic classification maps of pre and post-event data are compared to create damage maps. But analysis of huge volumes of high resolution image data for rapid damage assessment is a challenging task to do with existing semi-automated imagery exploitation techniques and the processes are time consuming. Also image data available immediately after the event may have variations in illumination due to cloud cover, different viewing angle compared to pre-event images and spatial co-registration variations leading to difficulties in identifying structural damages, changed or affected areas by directly comparing thematic maps. Automated Image analysis that captures and explores images based on their structural content can be used for effectively identifying damaged areas. In this paper we present an automated technique that indexes bi-temporal images using robust features based on their structural content and identify damaged and affected areas by analyzing the indexed features.

II. FEATURE EXTRACTION

Various spectral and spatial features have been used for indexing remote sensing images. We used the structural and texture features as they are robust to illumination variations and changes to atmospheric conditions during image acquisition when compared to color and spectral features [5]. Local binary pattern (LBP), local edge pattern (LEP) and Gabor texture features were used to index the images based on their content. LBP based features have been used in various applications like face detection, image analysis and image retrieval because of its better tolerance to illumination changes. The LBP is computed by using a moving window operator and producing a binary pattern by thresholding the window elements by the center pixel [6]. The binary pattern is assigned to the center pixel. The histogram of the binary patterns in an image is computed and used. The LBP values encode different patterns like line edges, spots and corner to their corresponding patterns

under varying illuminations. E.g. a spot (a dark pixel surrounded by bright pixels all around) and relatively brighter spot yield similar LBP values.

125	145	150
125	70	150
125	145	150

a) Spot

1	1	1
1	0	1
1	1	1

(c) LBP for Spot

225	240	225
225	120	225
248	240	225

(b) Brighter Spot

1	1	1
1	0	1
1	1	1

(d) LBP for Brighter Spot

Figure 1: LBP values are similar for different illumination conditions.

The LEP is similar to the LBP but extracted from edge maps rather than pixel intensity values [1]. LEP patterns also take into consideration the value of the center pixel and it can be either 1 (edge) or 0 (not an edge). Typically buildings and other structural features have strong edge patterns. LEP captures the changes in structural edge patterns. Also debris from damaged structures leads to edges distributed in a random fashion as illustrated in figure 2, which can be captured by variations in LEP.

Figure 2 Edge maps from before and after event images indicating random edge patterns for some damaged areas

Gabor filtering has been extensively used for various automated image texture analysis tasks. Texture analysis requires finer bandwidth filters to differentiate among

different textures and also requires good spatial localization to identify the location within an image. The Gabor filters have been shown to minimize the joint 2D uncertainties in space and frequency making them best suited for texture analysis [7]. Gabor filters are band pass filters and have the shape of a Gaussian envelope modulated by a harmonic function. A two dimensional Gabor function can be written as

$$h(x, y) = s(x, y)g(x, y) \quad (1)$$

Where, $s(x, y)$ is the sinusoidal function and $g(x, y)$ is the Gaussian envelope.

$$s(x, y) = \exp(-2\pi j(u_0x + u_0y)) \quad (2)$$

$$g(x, y) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\sigma_x\sigma_y}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{x^2}{\sigma_x^2} + \frac{y^2}{\sigma_y^2}\right)\right) \quad (3)$$

The frequency response of the filter $H(u, v)$ can be written as

$$H(u, v) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_u\sigma_v} e^{\left(\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{(u-u_0)^2}{\sigma_u^2} + \frac{(v-v_0)^2}{\sigma_v^2}\right)\right)} \quad (4)$$

Where, $\sigma_u = 1/2\pi\sigma_x$ and $\sigma_v = 1/2\pi\sigma_y$.

The filters in equation (4) are shifted by u_0 and v_0 to analyze different portion of the frequency domain or at different scales in the image domain. To analyze textures with different frequency patterns a bank of Gabor band pass filters which sample the frequency space optimally with different peak frequency and orientation was used. The filter bank provides a framework to analyze textures at various spatial scales and orientations.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

To evaluate the damage assessment features with hurricane Katrina data two IKONOS images obtained on September 30, 2003 and September 2, 2005 were used. The images covered approximately a 60 Sq. Km. area covering the Biloxi, Gulfport area in Mississippi Gulf Coast which had significant structural damage. We experimented with creating damage assessment maps at pixel level and at a regional level. The studies were conducted to analyze the scale, accuracy and robustness with which damage assessment maps can be created for time critical needs. For the region based approach the bi-temporal images were tessellated in to small tiles representing a 64 m x 64m area on the ground. In the region based approach, features which

quantify spatial texture and structural content of the image data tiles (13532 tiles) were extracted. This provides for some robustness when small co-registration errors and variations in view angle of the images are present. A 36 bin histogram of the LBP features, 72 bin histogram of the LEP feature and 36 Gabor filter features (3 scales, 6 orientations and 2 features for each scale and orientation) was computed. The images were indexed with a 144 (36+72+36) length

feature vector. The feature extraction process is compute intensive and slow, but considerable speed up can be achieved by using parallel processing using a data parallel approach [8]. The features were compared for changes by comparing the angle between the principal components of the feature vector. The feature comparison was done only over land regions.

(3a) Before Katrina, IKONOS Image

(3b) After Katrina IKONOS image

(3c) Damaged Areas

Legend

- No significant Damage
- Damage

Figure 3 : Damaged Areas identified using a region based approach.

(4a) Before Image

(4b) After Image

(4c) Damaged Areas

Figure 4: Damaged Areas identified using a pixel level comparison

IV. SUMMARY

An automated technique to identify damaged areas from high resolution imagery was presented. The preliminary results indicate some robustness to illumination variations and small co-registration errors. This methodology can be used to identify damaged areas for time critical usage for first responders and decision support systems. The feature extraction stage which is computationally intensive could be speeded up by using high performance computing. Also pre-event imagery could be indexed as part of disaster preparedness effort for predicted and forecasted natural disaster events like hurricanes. A more robust and effective methodology to index and identify the difference between the features is being investigated.

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